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SYNYTSIA S. V.

Digitalisation as a platform for innovative development of IT enterprises in the context of globalisation transformations

The subject of the research is the theoretical and practical foundations of digitalization as a platform for innovative development of IT enterprises in the context of globalization transformations.

The aim of the research is to analyze the role of digitalization in the development of IT enterprises in the context of globalization transformations, as well as to identify the main trends and obstacles associated with this process.

Research methods. In the course of the research, the methods of literary analysis, induction and deduction, empirical research, graphical method, method of socio-economic analysis were used.

Results of the investigation. It has been determined that globalization promotes the spread of digital technologies and encourages transformational changes in various sectors of the economy, and that is why digitalization is becoming a necessary basis for the innovative development of IT enterprises, which allows them to adapt to the requirements of the modern world. It is established that the innovative development of enterprises is associated with the introduction of new technologies, management methods and approaches to production, which ensure improvement of productivity and quality of products and services. It is proved that digitalization contributes to the creation of new business models, digital products and services, and provides access to global markets and partnerships.

Scope of the results. Digital economy, Entrepreneurship and business, Economics.

Conclusions. Thus, digitalization is a key element of the innovative development of IT enterprises in the context of globalization transformations, which contributes to improving the efficiency of business processes, creating new products and services, and opening up new opportunities for international cooperation. However, for the effective digitalization of enterprises, it is necessary to take into account certain obstacles, such as the lack of qualified personnel, high costs of technology implementation, and the rapid pace of technological change. In general, digitalization is becoming not just a trend, but a prerequisite for the successful development of IT enterprises in the modern world, so to achieve competitive advantages and sustainable development in the global market, enterprises should invest in the introduction of digital technologies, staff training and cybersecurity.

Keywords: digital economy, globalization, transformation, innovative development, IT enterprises, digitalization, cybersecurity, sustainable development.

СИНИЦЯ С. В.

Діджиталізація як платформа інноваційного розвитку ІТ-підприємств в умовах глобалізаційних трансформацій

Предметом дослідження є теоретично–практичні основи діджиталізації як платформи інноваційного розвитку ІТ-підприємств в умовах глобалізаційних трансформацій.

Метою дослідження є аналіз ролі діджиталізації у розвитку ІТ-підприємств в умовах глобалізаційних трансформацій, а також визначення основних тенденцій розвитку та перешкод, пов'язаних із цим процесом.

Методи дослідження. В ході наукового дослідження було використано методи літературного аналізу, індукції та дедукції, емпіричного дослідження, графічний метод, метод соціально–економічного аналізу.

Результати роботи. Визначено, що глобалізація сприяє поширенню цифрових технологій та спонукає до трансформаційних перетворень в різних галузях економіки, і саме тому діджиталізація стає необхідним базисом для інноваційного розвитку ІТ–підприємств, яка дозволяє їм адаптуватися до вимог сучасного світу. Встановлено, що інноваційний розвиток підприємств пов'язаний з впровадженням нових технологій, методів управління та підходів до виробництва, що забезпечують поліпшення продуктивності та якості продукції і послуг. Доведено, що діджиталізація сприяє створенню нових бізнес–моделей, цифрових продуктів і послуг, забезпечує доступ до глобальних ринків і партнерств.

Галузь застосування результатів. Цифрова економіка, підприємництво та бізнес, економіка.

Висновки. Отже, діджиталізація є ключовим елементом інноваційного розвитку ІТ–підприємств в умовах глобалізаційних трансформацій, яка сприяє підвищенню ефективності бізнес–процесів, створенню нових продуктів та послуг, а також відкриває нові можливості для міжнародного співробітництва. Проте для ефективної діджиталізації підприємств необхідно враховувати деякі перешкоди, такі як брак кваліфікованих кадрів, високі витрати на впровадження технологій та швидкі темпи технологічних змін. Загалом, діджиталізація стає не просто трендом, а необхідною умовою успішного розвитку ІТ–підприємств у сучасному світі, тому для досягнення конкурентних переваг та сталого розвитку на глобальному ринку, підприємствам слід інвестувати у впровадження цифрових технологій, навчання персоналу та забезпечення кібербезпеки.

Ключові слова: цифрова економіка, глобалізація, трансформація, інноваційний розвиток, ІТ–підприємства, діджиталізація, кібербезпека, сталий розвиток.

Formulation of the problem. In the current environment of rapid development of information technology and globalization processes, digitalization has become a key factor in the innovative development of IT enterprises, opening up new opportunities to improve the efficiency of business processes, create new products and services, and provide competitive advantages in the global market. Globalization promotes the spread of digital technologies and encourages transformational changes in various sectors of the economy. In this regard, digitalization is becoming a necessary basis for the innovative development of IT enterprises, allowing them to adapt to the requirements of the modern world. The innovative development of enterprises is associated with the introduction of new technologies, management methods and production approaches that improve the productivity and quality of products and services. Digitalization plays a key role in this process, as it facilitates the creation of new business models, digital products and services, and provides access to global markets and partnerships.

In the context of globalization, IT enterprises can use digitalization to scale their operations internationally and respond quickly to changing market conditions. Globalization facilitates the rapid spread of information and communication technologies

(ICT) and the creation of a single digital space, which allows IT enterprises to more easily introduce new products and services, expand markets, and collaborate with partners from other countries. However, globalization also creates significant obstacles, including increased competition, which forces businesses to look for innovative solutions to maintain a competitive position in the market.

Analysis of research and publications on the problem. The study of digitalization as a basis for innovative development is an active field of research, where foreign and domestic authors have made a significant contribution to the study of this issue. Among the main foreign authors who have studied digitalization and innovative development are the following: Eric Schmidt and Jonathan Rosenberg, who have studied how digital technologies have transformed business models and how companies can use innovation to succeed in the digital environment. Klaus Schwab, who describes how digitalization and new technologies are driving the fourth industrial revolution and how this affects innovation in various fields. Clayton Christensen analyzed technological innovations that can destroy existing markets and create new ones, and how this is related to digitalization and its impact on innovation. Michael Porter explored strategies

for achieving competitive advantage and the role of information technology in this process. Garry Stern explored the role of information technology in digital transformation and its impact on the innovative development of enterprises. James Keller analyzed the managerial aspects of digital transformation and their impact on innovative development. Martin Lindstrom explored how small data and digital tools can reveal big trends and drive innovation. These authors provide deep insights into how digitalization affects the innovative development of enterprises and can serve as useful resources for understanding this topic. Among domestic researchers, it should be noted: Arefieva, O., Chaika M., Chkan A., Harafonova O., Hirniak K., Husieva O., Ilin V., Ivanyshyn A., Kasai P., Kolodnenko N., Kovalenko N., Kuchmiiova T., Kulyk A., Kyrychenko N., Lazebnyk L., Lazorenko T., Lehominova S., Lemeshchenko N., Lozhachevska O., Lyshenko M., Makarenko N., Marova S., Mikhieienko K., Obikhod S., Olshanska O., Oviechkina, O., Polyvoda V., Puzyrova P., Raichuk I., Sholom I., Synytsia S., Timynskyi O., Tkachuk V., Vlasenko V., Voitenko O., Zhosan H., Zimina N. and others. However, the issue of digitalization as a basic platform for the innovative development of IT enterprises in the context of globalization transformations still requires a clear definition and in-depth research.

Presenting main material. Innovative development of enterprises is associated with the introduction of new technologies, management methods and production approaches that improve productivity and quality of products or services. Digitalization plays a key role in this process, as it facilitates the creation of new business models, digital products and services, and provides access to global markets and partnerships [1; 2; 3].

In the context of globalization, IT enterprises can use digitalization to scale their operations internationally and respond quickly to changing market conditions. Globalization facilitates the rapid spread of information and communication technologies (ICT) and the creation of a single digital space, which allows IT enterprises to more easily introduce new products and services, expand markets, and collaborate with partners from other countries. However, globalization also creates significant obstacles, such as increased competition, forcing businesses to look for innovative solutions to maintain their competitive position in the market [4; 5; 6; 7; 8].

Digitalization is the process of transition from analog to digital technologies in various fields of activity, including business, economy, society and public administration, which involves the integration of digital tools such as automation, artificial intelligence, big data, the Internet of Things (IoT), cloud computing and other innovative technologies that allow to increase productivity, efficiency and competitiveness. The main definitions of digitalization are shown in Fig. 1 [9; 10; 11; 12; 13; 14].

In a globally competitive environment, innovation is becoming a key factor in securing competitive advantage, where IT enterprises must invest in research and development to implement new ideas and technologies. For IT enterprises, digitalization is becoming not only a tool for increasing efficiency, but also a means of adapting to the new conditions of globalization transformations. Digitalization allows businesses to respond more quickly to changes in the market environment, increase the flexibility of business processes, and ensure integration with international partners. In particular, digitalization facilitates the creation of digital platforms for collaboration, data exchange, and joint development of innovative solutions [15; 16; 17].

One of the main trends of digitalization is the active use of big data and artificial intelligence (AI) technologies, which allow IT companies to analyze large amounts of information, automate decision-making processes and develop personalized products and services. Cloud computing allows businesses to scale their operations and provide access to information resources from anywhere in the world, which is especially important for IT enterprises operating in the global market, as cloud platforms provide flexibility and data security. The Internet of Things (IoT) enables the creation of new products and services based on the interaction of physical and digital objects, such as smart devices or intelligent control systems [18; 19; 20].

With the development of digitalization, cybersecurity and data protection issues are becoming increasingly important, which is why IT companies must ensure the security of their information systems and the protection of users, personal data, which requires the implementation of modern cybersecurity technologies and constant monitoring of possible threats. The impact of globalization on IT enterprises is manifested in the following key aspects: expansion of markets and growth opportuni-

Main definitions of digitalization and digital technologies in the globalized world

Source: [9; 10; 11; 12; 13; 14]

ties; increased competition; technological innovation and knowledge sharing; logistics and supply chain management; cultural and legal aspects; the need for adaptability and flexibility; and increased requirements for quality and innovation. Let's look at each of these aspects in more detail [21; 22; 23].

Globalization allows IT companies to enter new international markets, expanding their customer base, which opens up new opportunities for growth and revenue. Also, IT companies can establish partnerships with companies from other countries, which provides access to new technologies, investments and innovations. IT companies have to compete not only with local but also with international companies, which increases the level of competition [24; 25; 26].

Globalization can lead to price instability for services and products, as international competitors can influence market pricing. Globalization facilitates the rapid exchange of technology and knowledge between countries, which allows IT enterprises to implement innovative solutions and use advanced technologies.

International collaborations can facilitate the co-development of new products and technologies, which allows for competitive advantage [27; 28].

Globalization affects supply chain management, including component procurement, data processing, and customer service. IT enterprises can leverage global resources to optimize their processes. Global supply chains can create obstacles, such as coordination between different countries, risk management, and quality assurance. IT enterprises must consider cultural differences in international markets when developing products and providing services, which can affect marketing strategies, user experience, and support. Globalization also means that different legal and regulatory requirements must be met in each country, so IT businesses must adapt their strategies to local laws, particularly in terms of data protection, intellectual property, and taxes. IT enterprises must quickly adapt to changes in the global environment, including economic fluctuations, technological innovations, and changes in market conditions [29; 30; 31].

Therefore, to operate effectively in the context of globalization transformations, IT enterprises can use flexible business models that allow them to respond quickly to changes and provide a high level of customer service. Particular attention is paid to globalization, which is manifested in increased requirements for the quality of products and services, and that is why IT enterprises must constantly improve their products to meet high quality standards.

Conclusions

Thus, digitalization is a key element of innovative development of IT enterprises in the context of globalization transformations, which contributes to increasing the efficiency of business processes, creating new products and services, and opens up new opportunities for international cooperation. However, for the effective digitalization of enterprises, it is necessary to take into account certain obstacles, such as the lack of qualified personnel, high costs of technology implementation, and the rapid pace of technological change. In general, digitalization is becoming not just a trend but a prerequisite for the successful development of IT enterprises in the modern world, so to achieve competitive advantages and sustainable development in the global market, businesses should invest in the implementation of digital technologies, staff training and cybersecurity.

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